

doi:10.5281/zenodo.19060502

Understanding Discipline In Educational Institutions

Douglas O. Nwaokugha¹ & Amandem Ozoemene Nworgu²

Department of Educational Foundations
Faculty of Education

University Of, Port Harcourt, Port Harcourt, Nigeria

¹Email: douglas.nwaokugha@uniport.edu.ng/GSM: 08060815940

²Email: memenworgu@yahoo.com/GSM: 07034386164

ABSTRACT

Discipline is an attractive concept both as a practice and as a process and its attractiveness makes it a norm that individuals, institutions and states that are desirous of genuine and quality sustainable individual and national development make a topmost priority. Deriving its centrality in achieving individual and national development, discipline in most cases admits peculiar idiosyncratic interpretations and applications for individuals and institutions. Using the philosophical methodology and theoretically guided by social constructivism and postmodernism, this study robustly creates insights for understanding discipline in educational institutions. In strong terms, the paper condemns practices where educational constitutions rely on external control mechanisms that are mainly punitive in their attempts to exercise discipline on learners but makes a strong case through instruction for the exercise of discipline that targets instilling in learners the ability to demonstrate self-discipline, self-control and other moral and ethical consciousness that are acceptable to members of the society. The paper makes some recommendations, part of which is that the teacher as a central and influential figure in discussions that revolve around discipline should first discipline himself through his exemplary life as a role model within and outside the school, variables that pose and cause disciplinary challenges are multifaceted and educational institutions should gear up to address them and teacher education institutions must face reality by incorporating disciplinary challenges as part of the core instructions for teacher education programmes in the 21st century among other recommendations.

Keywords: Discipline, education, educational institutions

INTRODUCTION

Living in an environment where there are order and social harmony is the dream and aspiration of peace loving and rational thinking individuals and many societies across the globe strive to ensure that an environment where order and social harmony prevail is maintained. Individuals and societies that make peace and social harmony norms in their environments enjoy the blessings of nature that come in the form of their ability to explore their environment, find happiness and fulfilment in all their actions, activities and endeavours. The prevalence of peace and happiness in the lives of such individuals' guides, illuminates direction and adds quality in the form of peace of mind, emotional stability, absence of crises and drive for higher achievements whose added advantages include living longer and acquiring skills and dispositions for overcoming challenges that are ever-present in the affairs of man and his institutions. People who live in environment where order, peace and social harmony prevail are more creative, more productive, more critical and usually experiences less conflict, less crises and less confusions. In fact, the

prevalence of order, peace and social harmony are foundational and fundamental requirements for human capital development, increase in productivity, progress and development in the life of an individual, that of a group and that of the state and her institutions.

One condition that must be present in the affairs of the individual, his institutions and the state as a prerequisite for individuals and institutions of the state to actualize their aspirations and the philosophy upon which such aspirations are established is to ensure that there is a conscious and concerted orientation that makes it a topmost priority that everyone who is linked or associated with or who, presides over the affairs of individuals or institutions of the state must make discipline a guiding principle. This is to say that any individual or any state that is conscious of initiating revolutions that target fairness equity, justice, respect for human rights, empowerment, and emancipation, social justice or any other humane concept that prioritizes the common advancement and development of humanity in any of its ramifications must first of all ensure that her citizens, who are the agents, instruments, and carriers of the genes of such advancement or development must allow and align their activities to be guided by conscience, self-confidence, self-control, voice of reason and moral rationality. A people who individually and collectively are guided by these can be said to be disciplined or can be said to be acting within the frame of reference of a people who are disciplined. To be disciplined is for individuals or the state to correspond their behaviours, actions and activities along lines where every citizen- the rich, the poor, the political, economic and the religious class demonstrate self-control, maintain order, social harmony, peace and decorum as a mark of wisdom and show of maturity irrespective of whatever provocations in the affairs of the individual or in the affairs of the state.

What may be figured out in discussions that border on discipline is that it is a conglomerate of behavioural and attitudinal dispositions that at its centre emphasizes the demonstration of traits of self-control and self-confidence in every action and activity of the individual and institutions of the state. To this end, discipline is inclusive and comprehensive so much that no institution of any kind anywhere in the world, be it cultural, social, military, para-military, financial, judicial, medical, or diplomatic institutions etc can make progress without such institutions marrying into their policy and administrative structures and machinery the seal of discipline. Such institutions and organizations must conduct their activities and affairs in a manner that those who watch them from a distance can notice that members of such institutions and organizations allow discipline to dictate the course of their actions. Not compromising discipline in an institution or organization positions such institutions or organization for greater relevance in the drive and quest of such institution or organization for quality service delivery to humanity and at the same time bring honour and respect to those at the helm of affairs of such institution or organization while compromising discipline in institutions or organizations stripes such institutions or organizations any trace of honour and respect from the members of the society. In all sincerity and honesty, the extent in which discipline is maintained and made a norm in any institution or organization is a scale, an index and a litmus test for determining the accountability, responsibility and credibility of such institution or organization and the level of responsiveness of those at the helm of affairs of such institutions or organizations. In fact, it is a scale and index for predicting the future of a people including the level of political, economic, social, moral, scientific and technological developments that a people and their state can experience. This revelation points in the direction that the ability of humanity globally to sustainably flourish heavily depends on the extent in which discipline is made a norm in the state so much that every citizen irrespective of class, position and power can act in ways that discipline guides all the actions of man in relationships with the self, fellow citizens, the state and nature.

The foregoing means that discipline is important for the individual and collective well-being of the citizens and institutions in the state and has naturally been the capstone of virtually all institutions that are charged with the responsibility of structurally engineering revolutions for bringing about reforms and transformations in the life of man and his institutions. One such institution that readily comes to mind in discussions that border on order and social harmony and that is charged with the responsibility of engineering revolutions for reforms and transformations especially reforms and transformations which ensure that discipline becomes a norms in the affairs of individuals and the state, upon which humanity and his institutions can sustainably and progressively advance is education.

Education is a social provision that states rely upon for introducing moral, social, political, economic, agricultural, environmental, scientific, technological and general innovations. It is an institution that targets providing information, directions, guides and reorientations for repositioning the citizens so as to enable citizens to qualitatively respond to change in the society in the form of providing citizens critical and creative capital with which they can initiate autonomous moral thinking as well as develop skills and capacity for challenging the status quo, a social justice, rational morality- laden and dynamic mechanism for entrepreneurially empowering the citizens of a state through providing equal opportunities, which inherently preoccupies itself with developing in citizens the ability and capacity to be creative, critical, reflective, analytical and productive especially in directions where citizens of a state can see and explore opportunities for their individual survival and the collective survival of their state.

It has to be pointed out that states that have made their marks globally are those states that have made the right investments in education, as any state that is desirous of quality investments in its human capital development must look up to its education industry for translating such lofty theoretical goals into practice and states that have successfully made this a norm have systematically positioned their citizens for actions- civic, economic, political, revolutionary etc and these have potentials to trigger quality progress and development in the state. This is because such states have consciously created epical and phenomenal awareness in their citizens that can make them to be alert on issues of marginalization, injustice, deprivation and enslavement, development that in totality are agents and instruments of retrogression and underdevelopment in the hands of the state and in the hands of fellow citizens.

The revelations above point in the direction that provision of education increases and heightens the inclination of citizens for creative, critical and civic-mindedness. As these are desirable attributes that parents and states want from citizens, both parents and the state regard education as a critical provision, which no responsible parent and no responsible state should deny the citizens. This attitude of parents and the state about education for the citizens identifies education as a foundational and fundamental provision and correspondingly a basic human right of every citizen, which on no account should be denied anyone. By making education a fundamental human right of every citizen, parent and the state have recognized its importance and correspondingly subscribe to the idea that a basic benchmark should be constitutionally established at least as a threshold and a basic entry point on the education ladder, which every child must get up to in order to function effectively in an ever-changing and complex world. It is strongly believed that getting to such a threshold can enable individuals to meaningfully contribute to their personal growth and development and to the growth and development of their state.

All the above positive compliments that education is associated with point in the direction that in addition to being inclusive and comprehensive, education holds the key to modernization, is the index or yardstick for assessing or evaluating the quality of life of the people, a litmus for placing a state on the development map, which equally has potentials for unlocking gates and doors that bar people from having access to opportunities. In fact, education empowers people for actions that are conducive for sustainable growth and development. It is on these premise that Shively (2005) can be said to be one hundred percent correct when he writes that responsible states make the provision of education a topmost priority among social services that they provide for their citizens and Nwaokugha (2025:22) caps it up when he writes that:

One consciously established institution that is charges with the general responsibility of ordering, reordering and overseeing the construction and reconstruction, formation, reformation and transformation of the society and its members so much that the seal and aura of positive change, positive reformation and positive transformation become a visible priority in the affairs of man and his institutions is education.

The ability of education to break monumental frontiers and make phenomenal progress in the history of man and his institutions is strongly hinged on the fact that the education industry strongly promotes discipline and does not compromise or is zero tolerant on issues of indiscipline. Put slightly different, parents, the society and the entire humanity hold the education industry and its personnel responsible for all the reforms and transformations which the learners in the education industry require and need or which should come about due to the various rigorous discipline and disciplinary measures that the learners in the education industry ought to receive in the course of their education in the various education institutions.

True, educational institutions by their nature and core mandate of reforming, correcting and transforming human beings mete out or unleash discipline and disciplinary measures, sometimes on the request of the parents and the members of the society to learners in the educational institutions. Regrettably, the same parents and members of the society who make or put up these requests for discipline and disciplinary actions or measures against learners in educational institutions whose behaviours and attitudes fall excessively short of requirements, most times turn against and deny the personnel of the education industry of their request for discipline and disciplinary actions or measures in educational institutions, a development that in most cases make caricature of the personnel of the education industry by exposing them to very high profile risks and public ridicule that at the end cause them emotional instability, loss of professional competence, psychological and psychical agony, loss of respect, physical pains in the forms of assault and insult, loss of their job and imprisonment or even death.

As serious and prevalent as issues that are linked to discipline and disciplinary actions and measures in the schools and educational contexts can be, not much scholarly attention has been given to this subject matter in the forms of creating adequate awareness and insights about it that can stimulate insights, creative and critical thoughts or reflections on it by stakeholders and members of the general public in the form of generating ideas that can guide stakeholders to appropriately understand discipline in schools and educational contexts on one hand and develop humanely receptive approaches for responding to it. This study is specifically undertaken to fill this gap.

This study on understanding discipline in the school and educational context can be significant in a number of ways. All things being equal, this study can create awareness and insights on causes and sources of indiscipline whose prevalence triggers intensified calls for discipline and disciplinary actions and measures in the education context. By creating this awareness, this study can sensitize learners and the members of the general public on how our singular and collective actions and inactions promote and propel the wheels of indiscipline in the society on one hand and create the required curiosity that can sensitize learners and the masses on creative strategies for minimizing the occurrence of indiscipline at the same time. In fact, the study can philosophically, socially and psychologically discuss discipline in its polymorphous nature and specifically, highlight what can be the focus of discipline in the school and educational context. Such inclusive and comprehensive discussion of discipline can help generate robust ideas about discipline that can guide learners and the general public in understanding the concept as well as to make discipline a norm in schools and educational contexts. Such robust understanding of the concept of discipline can inherently sensitize learners and the masses that a society whose citizens make discipline a norm in their lives have laid formidable foundations for addressing social, moral, political, philosophical, economic and general problems of humanity and these have positive implications for the development of the individual and the national development of the states.

The study can create insights and awareness on the implications and dangers of the prevalence of indiscipline in the society generally and in school and educational contexts in particular. By this inclination, the study can pointedly make a case for discipline to be the focus and cardinal norm in the society generally and in schools and educational contexts in particular. The study can specifically be significant in radically and revolutionally charting and kick-starting new directions, new orientations, new narratives and new beginnings that can in addition to widening the scope of instruction and knowledge base of teachers expand the epistemological space for teacher education institutions, teacher re-education programmes and scope of policy formulation and policy implementation as it concerns human capital development and national development of states.

The study can create awareness among education stakeholders concerning what to expect from learners and possible new behaviours that teachers can demonstrate within and outside the school that can align with the attitudes of people who are desirous of making discipline a norm in schools and in the society. By implication, this study can stimulate curiosity on curricular and pedagogical strategies for guiding teachers and learners on skills and dispositions that can be conducive for discipline and disciplinary measures in schools and educational contexts in particular and society generally.

This study is theoretically guided by two theories namely; social constructivism and postmodernism. Social constructivism according to Ageeva (2016:1) is also called social constructionism and makes wave

in knowledge construction, knowledge building and knowledge generation. Part of why this is the case is that many scholars of different disciplines and areas of specialization embrace social constructivism as their destination of choice in their curiosity, quest and desire to construct, build and generate knowledge. The receptivity of scholars to social constructivism is basically anchored on the key premise of the theory namely; mankind produce, generate, construct and build knowledge, ideas and meaning from his interrogation, curiosity and interactions with his daily experiences and ideas. In other words, ideas and knowledge of whatever configurations are social phenomena and are correspondingly socially constructed through a combination of forces of the environment and the various experiences of the constructor of the knowledge. On the basis of the environment, environmental forces and the experiences of the various constructors of knowledge, Nwaokugha and Moses (2025:436), write that social constructivism as a theory of knowledge construction holds that creative insights, creative ingenuity, creativity and critical consciousness of man are the basic foundations and pillars of whatever knowledge that exists in any discipline in any society. A revelation which the above exposes is explicitly pointed out by Nwaokugha and Odinka (2025:180), when they write that the meaning of social constructivism as a theory of knowledge construction is that human beings are the architects, builders and constructors of whatever meaning that exists in the world of knowledge. The above remark is in agreement with the positions of Liu and Mathew (2005:387), who strongly maintain that “knowledge is not mechanically acquired but constructed with the constraints and offerings of the learning environment”.

What can be said to be the frame and structure of social constructivism as a theory of knowledge construction is hinted at by Nwaokugha (2025:24) in these words:

What is at the heart or centre of social constructivism as a theory of knowledge construction is the awareness that no knowledge of any configuration is ready made and correspondingly sampled or displayed anywhere to be purchased or hired by who wants it, rather knowledge of any configuration can be produced, generated and constructed through the conscious, critical and creative efforts of an individual or individuals who demonstrate creative engagement, commitment and critical consciousness in the search for knowledge.

In addition to the above, those who are interested in knowledge generation, construction and production using the trajectory of social constructivism must learn how to collaborate and cooperate, must have demonstrable skills and must demonstrate skills of critical and creative thinking, must be open to ideas and experiences especially experiences gained through engagement, participation, commitment and daily interactions and dialogues with other members of the society. Such persons must also show curiosity and interests in event and happening around them including demonstrating epical and phenomenal commitment to breaking new frontiers of knowledge whose emergence or evolution must be deployed and adapted to solving and resolving specific and general challenges or problems of man. In fact, such knowledge that has evolved must expand the frontiers of already existing knowledge in addition to responding to the demands of the phenomenon of change. The foregoing features and conditions that sequentially must be present in discussions that border on social constructivism as a theory of knowledge construction is systematically summarized by Nwaokugha and Keri-Frank (2023:83), when they write that ‘at the heart of social constructivism is the focal flashpoint that knowledge is not a property that the individual possesses alone rather, it is a shared experience that develops and circulates through social interactions.

Postmodernism as a theory of knowledge construction is usually one that cannot be adequately discussed without preliminary remarks and this has become a tradition among scholars, who in their attempts to discuss postmodernism always start in the past, precisely with a critical and creative look at modernism, which according to Silverman (1991:2), invokes a meaning that revolves around a break with tradition, a break with the past and a search for new self-conscious expressive form. What can be deduced from the above is that to be modern means to jettison and repudiate everything that is associated with the past and in place of the past, bring in those practices that are contemporary and demonstrate everything that is associated with the contemporary era. Modernism as a break the past and tradition is associated with epical and monument promises of radically and revolutionally improving and adding value to the

conditions of man in all ramifications but ingloriously modernism became a period in human history where according to Nwaokugha (2022:165) “citizens suffered and misery became norm so much that the combined blows of suffering and human misery passed levels human beings can endure and tolerate”. The inability of modernism to fulfill its promises of emancipation, empowerment and general improvement of the quality of life of the masses turned out to raise an alternative, this time, postmodernism, which some scholars simply prefer to refer to as period after modernism.

Postmodernism as a theory of knowledge construction enjoys a multiplicity of definitions as well as possesses interdisciplinary, multidisciplinary and cross disciplinary outlooks, thereby making it a theory of knowledge construction that many disciplines identify with. Inherent to postmodernism is the recognition that it is a way of approaching traditional ideas and practices in non-traditional ways that deviate from pre-established super structural mode and correspondingly postmodernism subscribes to the idea that nothing is absolute, nothing is fixed, that there are better ways of handling or addressing private, public and social issues, that a better world than the present one is possible, that all realities, no matter their configuration are social constructs and correspondingly have the ability and capacity to change, that all realities are subjective and that there is no absolute truth, that nothing in the affairs of man and the society is certain rather post-modernism is structured on the frame that makes case for continuous improvement and on the basis of this, man should have an optimistic and forward-looking orientation towards reality, including the curiosity to continuously evaluate and re-evaluate, examine and re-examine situations.

Anyone with the least sense of critical and analytic scrutiny or consciousness can realize that at the heart of postmodernism is the zeal, enthusiasm and curiosity that prioritizes “dismantling most of our normal ways of thinking about how meaning, interpretation and reality works (Zeeman, Poggenpoel, Myburgh & Van der Linde, 2002). What is instructive regarding the above assertion is that postmodernism strives to create a balance and is this balance, postmodernism sensitizes humanity with two visions namely, the ability and critical consciousness to creatively and critically look backward as well as to creatively and critically look forward at the same time, with an overriding aim of constantly improving situations or leaving impressions on situations that can be better than they were. However, in these backward and forward outlooks, it can be said that postmodernism is favourably disposed to the past, as it views the past to be axiologically richer in all ramifications and correspondingly the past should be constantly reviewed in order to modify and influence the present and the future. Any curious and serious observer of the foregoing can notice that postmodernism is seriously committed to making quality change a norm and correspondingly wants the seal of change to be noticed in the affairs of man and institutions of the state so much that products of such institutions can on their own become drivers of change. In a way, there should be no-one-size-fits all paradigm for judging reality, rather reality should be in a constant state of flux where what had happened in the past can serve as a guide and signpost for shaping the present and the future in positive directions.

Both social constructivism and postmodernism as theories of knowledge construction are suitable for this study. The suitability and appropriateness of social constructivism as a theory of knowledge construction for this study lies in its ability and capacity to create awareness and develop insights in learners and members of the knowledge community that knowledge construction evolves through the application and ability of one to be creative and critical, aided by systematic demonstration of norms of devotion, commitment and dedication by individuals or groups that are desirous of constructing knowledge, especially when they constantly participate and interact with their environment and other members of their society. When this is internalized or made to become norms, learners and members of the knowledge community can develop the ability and capacity that can keep the light of knowledge burning by converting whatever experiences they go through into knowledge, bearing in mind that human beings construct, build and develop knowledge or are the architects, builders and developers of whatever knowledge that exists, in which it is also the responsibility of any committed person in the knowledge industry to do so.

On the other hand, the appropriateness of postmodernism as a theory of knowledge construction for this study lies in the claim of the theory that realities are social constructions and correspondingly are not

fixed and are not absolute rather realities are relative and plural. This revelation and exposition give every member of the knowledge community equal opportunity to explore the multiplicity of perspectives that are embedded in reality especially when such conscious attempts have gone through the reflective processes of logical, creative, analytic and critical thinking. The idea of reality being linked to social construction, which is present in social constructivism as well as in postmodernism links social constructivism and postmodernism together as two theories of knowledge that travel on the same road.

Methodologically, any academic discourse where reality is linked to social construction harmoniously aligns well with the qualitative or philosophical research methodology, therefore in this study, the methodology that is deemed most appropriate is basically the qualitative or philosophical research methodology. Qualitative or philosophical research methodology is unique in knowledge construction, generation and production and part of why this is so is explained by Nwaokugha and Smith-Ogizeh (2025:159), when they write that the qualitative or philosophical research methodology offers researchers and scholars robust and receptive epistemological space to freely and robustly express and communicate their ideas to the knowledge world and success in this direction is made possible simply because qualitative or philosophical research methodology, according to Angadi (2019) relies on the collection of extensive narrative data on many variables over an extended period of time in a naturalistic setting to gain insights that are not possible using any other types of research methods. Unique to this type of research methodology is the fact that the scholar or the researcher who uses it is usually the instrument for data collection. Data collection for qualitative or philosophical research is usually in extensive narrative forms and for such data that are in extensive narrative form to qualify as instrument for the construction and generation of knowledge in philosophical research, they must go through what Nwaokugha and Moses (2025:438) call thorough analytic scrutiny and rigours of thought that target establishing semantic clarity and logical coherence.

We must state and state it very unambiguously that qualitative or philosophical research especially in education is seriously associated with creating insights on human and institutional actions and inactions and Ishtiaq and Naz (2024:10) call attention to this when they write that:

Qualitative research is often exploratory, aiming to uncover new insights, perspectives and understanding within educational settings. Qualitative research in education involves collecting and analyzing non-numerical data such as interviews, observations, case studies and document analysis. The aim is to generate in-depth insights, explore meanings and understand the underlying processes that shape educational phenomena.

Another dimension that gives qualitative or philosophical research methodology the edge it enjoys in the world of knowledge is that it incorporates what Nwaokugha and Danladi (2016) call speculation, analysis and prescription. It can be recalled that constructing, building and generating knowledge in its earliest time and up to the present is exclusively based on speculation and this has been acknowledged by Gire (2020), who writes that speculation as a qualitative or philosophical research methodology has been primordial to all experiences and thinking, an assertion according to Nwaokugha and Smith-Ogizeh (2020), which establishes that speculation is not a new comer in the world of knowledge. Sufficient evidences abound that testify that speculation as a method of qualitative or philosophical research methodology is primordial to all experiences. According to Currie (2021), speculation is fundamental and foundational for successful science, no wonder Nwaokugha and Agbarakwe (2024:253) write that speculation is interdisciplinary, multidisciplinary and cross-disciplinary. As a proof of its interdisciplinary, multi-disciplinary and cross-disciplinary nature, Nwaokugha and Smith-Ogizeh (2025:159) writes that speculation can be applied in philosophy and its applied disciplines, social sciences and natural sciences. In what can be called a context specific application of the concept of speculation, Swedberg (2021:46) identifies two main meanings of speculation as:

1. A risky but potentially very profitable economic activity, and
2. The making of conjectures without firm evidence.

In addition to the above, scholars have different definitions of speculation. According to Oduor (2010:97), to speculate is to wonder, conjecture, guess and to hypothesize. This definition aligns with one of the

meanings of speculation provided by Swedbery (2021) above. From a different perspective Aminigo (1999) and Agulanna (2011) defines speculation as a conscious attempt to find logical coherence in an entire realm of thought while Haung, Xie and Chen (2021), write that speculation or speculative thinking is that type of thinking about past and future possibilities, which includes counter factual thinking, pre-factual and other types of thinking.

Reference that speculation or speculative thinking is about past and future possibilities is very instructive and why this is so is that speculation serves as a wake-up call and a guide for sensitizing humanity into examining and re-examining human and institutional actions in the form of providing man with evaluative, creative and analytic lens upon which a new philosophy, a new way of doing things and a philosophy of action can evolve in man's quest, curiosity and desire to conquer, subdue and survive in his environment. Here, speculation serves as a provocateur of action in addition to raising curiosity and consciousness in the individual to know more. This accounts for why Nwaokugha and Nwaogu (2024), write that speculation and speculative thinking is the epistemological navigating compass and guide for reforms, transformations and innovations in the affairs of man and his institutions, a position in which Nwaokugha and Moses (2025:439) re-echo when they write that man indulges in speculation:

In order to reform, transform, transcend or transition to levels that are qualitatively better than his present state or more technically a behavioural disposition which man resorts to particularly when he is confronted and challenged by situations he cannot easily grasp or understand.

This is to say that every human being speculates and the speculation triggers in him the curiosity, desire, enthusiasm and the urge to know more about the puzzle before him and to take action and this is where it can be correct to say that there is no epistemological breakthrough that did not start with speculation. The modus operandi in speculation as a method of philosophical research is one in which the researcher aligns himself with the conventionally accepted practice in philosophical research so that he is guided by what Nwaokugha and Wogonwu (2023:4) call a sense of logical unity, logical coherence and logical clarity about the presentation that is the subject matter of the philosophical discourse. What this reveals and translates into is that the acceptability of whatever that has been presented by a scholar or a researcher as meeting the criteria of acceptance or qualifying as knowledge depends on the extent in which the conclusions of the scholar or researcher derive from the premise before them.

The ability to indulge in speculation is innate in everyone, however, there are disciplines that are more receptive to speculation, without which specialists in such disciplines cannot realistically and authentically perform. Scholars whose disciplines and area of specialisation exclusively focus on topics and issues that quickly change over a short period of time and scholars whose disciplines address issues or topics which do not have a one-size-fits-all answers to questions and issues they raise. The above accounts for why metaphysics and axiology (aesthetics, ethics, social philosophy and political philosophy) must be handled speculatively. Language and logic play instrumental roles in any effective and meaningful speculations.

Analysis as a method of philosophical studies or researches focusses on meaningful communications and making meaning and communication explicit and effective. Analysis as a philosophical research methodology is as old as man and has been a foundational and fundamental requirement and prerequisite in man's quest to understand himself and his environments. In fact, man's creative and critical consciousness to understand himself and his environment has revolved around man's ability to indulge in analysis. Analysis prioritizes clarity and precision in the use of language especially in communication. That the focus of analysis is on meaning and its clarification extends the business of analysis in philosophical research to the instruments or vehicles that are used in conveying meaning. This is the reason why analysis as a method of philosophical research preoccupies itself with the critical and creative examination of words, terms, concepts and propositions with the sole intention of making explicit whatever meanings that may be associated with such words, terms, concepts or propositions. When words, terms and concepts have been subjected to analytic scrutiny, such attempts and efforts provide opportunities for what Nwaokugha and Moses (2025), call semantic clarity and linguistic precision that help to eliminate ambiguity, absurdity, contradiction and ineffective or meaningless communication on

one hand and lay foundations for an environment of peace, unity cooperation and collaboration, where these morality and peace-promoting concepts become norms due to analysis, such efforts usually reduce to the barest minimum the occurrence of disagreements, crisis, conflicts and misunderstanding. We can recall that what has been responsible for wars, crises and conflicts in many societies across the globe has been faulty use of words, terms, concepts and faulty communication. It follows that when analysis is properly done, it has potential to instill or inculcate in people the dispositions to use words, terms, and concepts in their semantic environments, develops in people the ability to make peace through amicable resolution of conflicts, inculcates in people the ability and capacity to be precise in their use of words, terms and concepts, sensitizes the people on the development of the ability to be thorough, critical and coordinated in thoughts and above all develops in people the ability to be logical and sequential in presentation of ideas.

Facts that cannot be disputed are that people who embrace analysis as their destination of choice for their researches and other studies are usually credited with the aura of intellectual sophistication (Nwaokugha & Wogonwu, 2020), just the same way analysis is associated with potentials to radically and revolutionally all instigate resolutions that can expand the knowledge world. Marks of intellectual sophistication and expansion of the world of knowledge are recipes for national development and analysis is key for laying foundations that can bring this to fruition. Because analysis is associated with all the above, analysis, according to Nwaokugha and Rotimi-Aina (2025) has become the trending practice in scholarship and academic pursuit all over the world.

The modus operandi in analysis is one in which the analyst breaks down his subject matter into smaller components and at the same time demonstrate how each of the smaller components are related to the whole. Most scholars who embrace analysis preoccupy themselves with conceptual and linguistic analysis. Conceptual analysis is when an analyst focuses on establishing if the meaning that is ascribed to a concept is actually what that concept stands for while linguistic analysis focuses on sentences, namely to establish if the meaning that is ascribed to a sentence is actually the meaning the sentence expresses. Language and logic are instrumental, foundational and fundamental in any analysis.

Every research or study initiated by a scholar or researcher that is worth the name must at least target resolving some problems and this is one reason why the section of any study that contains ideas on the resolution of issues addressed in a study is usually very important. It follows that prescription as a methodology of carrying out philosophical research or study is usually that section in a researcher's or scholar's work where he consciously and autonomously proffers ideas or solutions that can lead to resolving and addressing the issues that he raised or discussed in the earlier sections of the study. Thus, Oduor (2010:97) says it all when he writes that to prescribe is to recommend or set down as a rule or guide. The idea above is said differently by Nwaokugha (2021:102), when he writes that prescription:

Is achieved in research in the form of the researcher making autonomous value statements on how an issue that has been the focus or subject matter of a philosophical discussion can be resolved so that all the wrongs noticed in the course of the discussion can be harmoniously addressed.

Prescription is a fundamental and foundational requirement of any good philosophical study, however, there are scholars and disciplines that without prescription, such disciplines and scholars may not render quality and sufficient service to the members of the society. Scholars in such area as axiology, (ethics, political philosophy, aesthetics and social philosophy) must prescribe and the reason for this is that such areas of specialization are easily affected by change and the quality of change at a particular point in time in the affairs of the members of the society easily influence and determine the next line of action that can be taken, a development that can cause a scholar or a researcher to prescribe something that is different from his earlier prescriptions.

The use of the qualitative or philosophical research methodology is appropriate and suitable for this study and this is because all human beings and institutions can benefit from the critical, analytic, creative and reflective touch, insights and consciousness, which the qualitative or philosophical research methodology brings to bear on studies. The methodology promises ground breaking breakthroughs as it helps to widen the vision of researchers and scholars, a development that enables scholars and researchers to view

researches and studies in certain areas of knowledge that seem unthinkable and un-contemplatable to be do-able and resolvable. This mindset that qualitative or philosophical research methodology develops in scholars and researchers is generally beneficial to the knowledge industry and national development of states. The qualitative or philosophical research methodology is supportive of cooperation and collaboration among scholars and researchers and lastly the qualitative or philosophical research methodology boost the confidence levels of scholars and researchers.

Scholars who choose qualitative or philosophical research methodology as their destinations of choice in researches and other academic discourse usually give detailed attention to concepts that are the focus of their studies and to this we now turn.

The Concept of Education

Education as a concept is associated with a plethora or multiplicity of definitions so much that one scholar alone can provide over a dozen definitions of the concepts. This development is usually traced to the root words, which scholars of education claim education is derived from and what has consequently followed this development has been scholars providing definitions of education that align with any particular root word such scholars subscribe to. In any case, what we can bear in mind is that definitions of educations as provided by the different scholars may be deep rooted in speculation, may be deep rooted in prescription and above all may be so elastic so much that there can be individualized, contextualized and stipulative definitions of education, which under serious critical and reflective scrutiny corresponds with features education is known for. From whichever perspective anyone views it, education is an instrument and institution for developing the human capital base of any state where the products are provided with creative, critical, reflective, analytical and entrepreneurial skills for their economic empowerment and for addressing and resolving specific and general issues that concern man and institutions in the state.

The same way there are definitional crises in defining education is the same way education is in terms of ways of using the concept. Scholars recognize that there are three ways of using the term education and the three ways are, education as a process, education as a product and education as a discipline. Education as a process invokes a meaning, that revolves around conscious and systematic efforts of a people and their state to develop, preserve and transmit the culture of a people from one generation to the other. Part of what this use of education implies is that education can be conceived of as a social provision that is provided through well-orchestrated structure, which, when provided through the right direction and right counselling helps citizens of a state to develop critical, reflective, creative and analytic insights upon which they can develop their God-given innate abilities, capabilities and socially acquired skills that can propel in them the curiosity, ability and capacity to be useful to themselves and the society at large. Again, education as a process fundamentally and foundationally serves as a dynamics, utilitarian and social justice mechanism through which a state can rely on for the social mobilization of her citizens so that such a state can on its own achieve her national developmental and general objectives. Education as a product focuses on the demonstration of qualities of educatedness such as possession of skills, display of sound morality that is expected of an educated person, demonstration of understanding and knowledge from those who claim to have gone through the process of education, while the use of education as a discipline means that education is a body of knowledge, where those who choose to study it rigorously go through the various theoretical and practical processes of mastering the intrigues, tricks, emotions, skills, characteristics of learners and those who sponsor them in educational institutions as well as the peculiarities of knowledge especially in the area of specialization of particular learner. In states where things fall into shape the way they are supposed to be, those who meet up the requisite requirements spelt out above are certified as meeting the condition for certification and correspondingly can lawfully practice as teachers.

Issues that border on the plethora of definitions and many ways in which education can be used vanish when focus is on the use of education for the common advancement of humanity. In fact, scholars of all configurations and colourations agree and recognize education as a foundational and fundamental social service any responsible state can rely on for its pursuit of public good as well as an instrument for sensitizing, conscientizing, forming, reforming and transforming its citizens in readiness for their navigating and transitioning to whatever levels of complexity and sophistication the state can be at any

point in time. So, providing education for the citizens of the state becomes a core mandate of the individuals, institutions and the state as providing it makes a people and their state and not providing it mars a people and their state. In fact, part of the justifications for the epical and phenomenal focus on education is provided by, Nwaokugha (2015:86), when he writes that providing education is a moral duty and a worthwhile, investment for correcting the ills of the past, shaping the present and securing the future. This can be the basis upon which education globally is recognized as a human right.

What is so special about education is that its provision in any state is not and cannot be neutral. Education according to Eboh (1996) is either for domestication or freedom. Any state that uses its provision of education for socializing her citizens where they become a band wagon of yes-member (Nwaokugha, 2015) and correspondingly cannot initiate actions that can initiate revolutions that can bring about reforms and transformations is merely domesticating her citizens whereas any state that provides education for her citizens as a way of opening their eyes and developing their creative and critical consciousness, where those who have received education can existentially and autonomously take their destiny in their own hands can be said to have received education for their freedom. Responsible states and societies use education as an instrument and institution for freedom and for freeing their citizens from the clutches of ignorance, injustice, marginalization, enslavement and deprivation.

The litmus for assessing the quality, functionality and suitability of educational provisions that states provide for their citizens is the extent in which such educational provisions instill and inculcate discipline in the citizens of the state. It is from the demonstration of discipline that the moral duties of education manifest in the affairs of individual members of the state, institutions of the state and the relationship between the state and her citizens can be tested.

The Concept of Discipline

Across primitive, civilized, sophisticated, developed, developing and underdeveloped states, one concept in human social dealing, or relationships and a norm that serves as institutional requirement for the development of individuals and the state that people are favourably disposed to is discipline. Part of the reason why people are favourably disposed to the concept of discipline is that discipline promotes orderliness, peace, harmony and development and individual, institutions and societies that maintain very high levels of discipline record phenomenal and astronomical growth and development. Because such individuals, institutions and states record very high levels of orderliness and development, they are rated very high in term of being credible, accountable, responsible and responsive in their dealing with members of the society. States and societies whose citizens adhere to the norms of discipline bring a lot of honour and international respect to their nations. It can be said with all amount of assurance and certainty that the concept of discipline has been present in the affairs of man and his institutions right from ancient time up to the present time but despite being ever present in the affairs of man or the length of time in which the concept has been, the concept is synonymous with different meanings and this feature of the concept makes it one concept that is prone to misunderstanding and misinterpretation. That this is the case accounts for why the concepts of discipline falls within the bracket of concepts whose usage is broad and at the same general. On the basis of this feature of the concept, it can be correct to say that the concept of discipline is robustly receptive to analysis.

The recognition of the fact that the concept of discipline is prone to misunderstanding, misinterpretation, and is broad and general makes the concept one that undergoes semantic shift or one that can be identified with chameleonic attributes that allow it to adapt and be applied in different contexts, ranging from military institutions, where the concept of discipline is a household name and a concept to be associated with individuals who observe strict compliance to rules and regulations of social life. The concept of discipline is also associated or linked to the concept of power. In all of these, one observation can be constant concerning concepts in this category and that observation is highlighted by Konstantinou, Chatzisavva and Logotheti (2022:5) when they write that concepts in this category do over time acquire positive and negative connotations. Discipline invokes positive meanings when it is a rationally, systematically and consciously initiated action whose target or aim is tailored and structured to guide the individual or institution into taking and undertaking reasonable and responsible actions and decisions whose sustenance can help to maintain and sustain the integrity and personality of the individual and his

institution. In this positive sense, discipline is an action one metes out or unleashes to a loved one whose sole target is to bring about reformation and transformation in the life of the receiver of the discipline or disciplinary actions. Discipline also stimulates an interpretation that revolves around a negative meaning and within this context or reference point, discipline and disciplinary measures are consciously taken actions whose meanings and intentions are to correct the receiver of the disciplinary actions for wrongs, not-too-good and undesirable actions the individual has done. Discipline in this perspective and frame of reference is in the same semantic context with punishment.

Whereas discipline and punishment may share the same semantic environment, there is a thin line that demarcates or separates the two concepts. Discipline can be taken as a systematic and conscious behavioural disposition that targets inculcating in people the development of voluntary behavioural disposition that develops in one the ability and disposition to autonomously obey rules and to live life that is guided by acceptable moral standards of the society, whereas punishment is punitive in nature and naturally must invoke unpleasant measures, actions and consequences on the part of an individual or group whose target is to reform and correct such individual or group. It must be pointed out very unambiguously that punishment is the aftermath, follow up and consequence of a moral failure, a moral short coming or a moral infraction on the part of the individual or group that is the receiver of the punishment. In fact, one thing that is central to punishment is the infliction of pain, imposition of unpleasant experiences and the withdrawal of rights and privileges from the individual or group that is being punished.

From the above, it is very obvious and clear that discipline falls within the bracket of concepts that are polymorphous and elastic and this position is taken simply because different authorities and scholars have different views about the meaning, use, role and objectives of disciplines in the life of the individual and the members of the society at large. Discipline according to Onderi and Odera (2012:710) can mean any of the following:

- i. Punishment, pain and fear,
- ii. Conscious attempt that concerns itself with correction of a wrong doer at home, in the school or at workplace
- iii. Discipline is also a specific means used to punish offenders, which is training through suffering, so it is a polite substitute for punishment

To Were (2006), discipline invokes a meaning that revolves around guiding the individuals to make responsible and reasonable decisions, while Constantinou et al (2022:59) see discipline as a process and a practice.

Any critical look at the foregoing can reveal that discipline is an action initiated and taken by man or an institution against man or an institution, which invokes meanings that gravitate between negative and positive directions, a development that creates a sharp division where scholars are boxed into camps or schools of thought and in these camps or schools of thought, some maintain that discipline is deeply rooted in negative meaning and has nothing to do with any positive connotation. To those who subscribe to this, discipline has nothing to do with any positive connotation. To those who subscribe to this, discipline has no aura of reformation and transformation attached to it. From the same angle, there are people whose own position is that discipline invokes a meaning that revolves around inflicting pain, suffering, agony, psychological and emotional fear on the victims or receiver of discipline and disciplinary actions. On the other hand, there are people whose outlooks on discipline implicate the concept in positive lights as they view it as deliberately and consciously taken action(s) usually by a superior, father or mother etc as part of efforts to bring about positive changes, reformations and transformations in the behaviour and life of a subordinate, son, daughter, ward etc. When viewed from this perspective, discipline is an action which an individual who loves another can mete out to him or her as his or her morally designed and orchestrated actions to humanely fix the senses of the receiver of the discipline or disciplinary actions in the right frame or in the right direction. Inherent in this line of thinking is the recognition that discipline should take place in a free atmosphere that has no trace of fear, intimidation and abuse, or should take place in context that is polite and firm.

Irrespective of camps or schools of thought any one belongs, all such persons recognize that discipline is associated with certain characteristics. Discipline is inclusive and comprehensive so much that scholars and institutions recognize it as a platform or channel for achieving all the ideals of education and moral autonomy and the extent in which citizens exhibit it serve as index for evaluating the efforts of the state in terms of translating the ideals of social justice, nationalism, patriotism, civic and citizens' participation in national discourse into reality. Justification for the above revolves around the fact that discipline is the hallmark and trademark upon which the development of character and the development of personality of citizens can be judged and the twin concept of development of character and development of personality, which are shaped by one's level of discipline combine to illuminate and reflect the level of self-confidence, level of sense of self control and development of a sense of judgement or evaluation that the individual demonstrates in local, national and international issues.

Discipline is fundamental and foundational in education so important that Onderi and Odera (2012:711) write that an institution or organization cannot function properly without discipline. This position is correct because discipline helps institutions and organisations to achieve their visions and goals in line with the trend of events in the society. Any institution or organization that pays no attention or less attention to issues of discipline has systematically and consciously introduced complex virus that can virulently destroy the soul and all what that institution and organization stands for or stand to achieve.

Discipline as a concept is important in the life of an individual and the smooth function of the state and its institutions. To qualify as being disciplined portrays that the person so described has or possesses the ability to make the development and manifestation of responsive and responsible behaviours norms in himself and the affairs of the society to the point that others can emulate him. This is why discipline is one core feature that differentiates responsible human beings or responsible society from irresponsible human beings and irresponsible society. What this suggests is that the level in which citizens of a state demonstrate how disciplined they are or the level of discipline that exists in a state can be index for ranking the state in terms of making it a destination for business and other image promoting decisions. In fact, the ability of citizens of a state, including those who hold elected and appointed positions to be disciplined or make discipline a norm is a yardstick for predicting the pattern and level of development that can exist in that state.

Every responsible society prays for her citizens to be responsible and where this is the norm, such a society can be said to have citizens who are disciplined. Any society where the citizens are disciplined can boost of persons who, on their own can initiate autonomous actions and behaviours, which in all ramifications can demonstrate how inclusive a state can be in terms of protecting and making case for the interests of all persons in the society and such persons can double by demonstrating behavioural traits where they morally respect themselves as well as everyone around them. Any society where the citizens are disciplined has consciously laid foundations for minimizing the occurrence of chaos, violent conflicts and confrontations, show of lawlessness and other behaviours that introduce confusion, unrest, reign of terror, anarchy and normlessness into the affairs of man and his institutions, In fact, discipline is the foundation for unity, development of depositions and ability to participate in peace-building mechanisms, peaceful coexistence and other dynamics that are supportive of conflict resolution. All these in a way point in the direction that discipline inherently embodies morality.

Societies or institutions where the members maintain the norms of discipline consciously instill in themselves moral, creative, articulative and productive skills that serve as conscience booster and conscience searching compass with which they can conveniently navigate the ever-complex and ever-changing world, where orchestrated and conscious efforts to introduce innovations are quickly overtaken by more complex innovative ideas before the latter is implemented. Here, the ability of any one to make the norms of discipline his guiding signpost becomes the saving grace for transitioning to the complex and contemporary world of the 21st century and beyond.

Through discipline, societies and institutions of the state systematically influence members of the society through living by example, administer and conscientiously transmit those value of their society and state from one generation to the other. It can be said with all amount of assurance and certainty that through discipline, societies and states develop in-built mechanisms that prioritize morality, belongingness, show

of love and mutual respect to the members of the society and between members of the society and institutions of the state. This development accounts for why Onderi and Odera (2012:710) write that one of the most effective tools use by an executive of an institution or organization is discipline and more pointedly that discipline particularly in schools and educational institutions creates an orderly atmosphere in which meaningful achievement of learning can take place and positive values, social skills and attitudes can be attained.

Part of why discipline is important particularly in schools and educational institutions is that it is a prerequisite for meaningful teaching and learning, which on its own is heavily dependent on a network of communications and interactions between students and students, between students and teachers, between school and other members of staff and between management of a school and the government. It has to be pointed out that in these chains of communications, there must be the seal and impression of discipline if the goal, aim and objectives of the school as a social institution is to be achieved. In fact, discipline guides all actions and activities in the school generally and in the classroom in particular so much that it is present in the organization of instructional objectives or contents, in the procedures to be taken by the teacher, in the step by step manner in which the teacher presents or communicates them to the learners, the way in which he interacts with the learners in the course of providing his instructions to them, in gatherings or deliberations involving teachers or the school and members of the larger society and above all, for discipline to be effective, its framing, formulation, application and implementation must wear a human face, be compassionate and be guided by moral rationality so much that it must be in strict compliance with rules that guide classroom, school and educational practices.

We can sound it loud and clear that a teacher's knowledge of his subject matter is not the only index for assessing his professional competence or the only platform that can enhance his level of productivity, rather, there are other variables, prominent among which are the extent in which the teacher can make order, normalcy or precisely discipline norms in his classroom in particular or in the school generally and the extent in which the teacher's interactions with the learners can trigger or stimulate in the learners behavioral dispositions that can align or challenge the learners to be sensitive, alert, critically minded and curious with issues that border on emancipation, justice, social justice, human rights, nationalism and fundamental freedoms especially in ways that promote self-discipline and self confidence in the learners.

Discipline as a moral virtue is highly cherished so much that every society and state prays that it should be a norm among citizens and institutions in the state but as obvious as this can be, discipline is epicly and phenomenally contentious. Mbithi (1974) recognizes and acknowledges this when he writes that one reason for making discipline a norm in every society and all sphere of life of man and his institution is the idea that the child is naturally wrong and corresponding needs to be corrected through the imposition of discipline and disciplinary actions in any of its ramifications. This position is in conflict with naturalism, a school of thought which maintains that man is sinless, is naturally a saint and is without any sense of wrong or evil. Naturalism is credited with strongly maintaining that whatever wrong a man manifest is due to interruption and interference from the adult and the environment in which man finds himself. In support of their claim, naturalists maintain that 'everything is good as it comes from the hands of the author of nature, but everything degenerates in the hands of man'.

Another contentious issue about discipline revolves around the ability of the concept to share the same semantic environment with punishment especially the justification that punishment is a legitimate way of securing submission and desired behaviour from those whose behaviours come short of what is socially acceptable. What this seems to pop up is an attitude of critical consciousness, critical reflection and critical scrutiny with a view to ascertaining if people who go through punishment as a result of one moral infraction or the other actually get reformed or transformed after the period of their punishment, bearing in mind that the aim of punishment is for the receiver of the punishment to transition to level of greater good in terms of abandoning those behaviours that caused him to be punished.

In reality what ought to be the case after punishment has been administered on those who commit moral infractions is a situation or case where the punishment or pain that has been inflicted on such persons brings about greater good or better changes in behaviour, but hardly does this happen, rather discipline and disciplinary actions against those who commit these moral infractions increase and multiply their

desire for the manifestation and demonstration of undesirable and socially unacceptable behaviours. In fact, the inability of those who received punishment to demonstrate signs of reformation and transformation or the idea of greater good calls for serious concern and the concern revolves around the fact that punishment is proper if and only if there is a decrease or no repeat of the same moral infractions, undesirable and socially unacceptable behaviours that caused the imposition or infliction of the earlier punishment, implying that the idea of punishment is defeated if the moral infractions upon which punishment as discipline was imposed continues to be demonstrated by the same people or the same group.

Sufficient attention has been given to the concept of discipline generally; focus can now be shifted to discipline in school and educational contexts.

Discipline in the Educational Context

Educational institutions are social organizations and as social organizations, they are epicentres and meeting points of people who come from different backgrounds, and who have different expectations from educational institutions. In the same way as different expectations exist among learners who are critical stakeholders in education, parents who sponsor the education of their children and wards equally come from different cultures, different socio-economic status, have different expectations and visions from that held by the teachers who are the managers of the educational institutions and again the core philosophy of the educational institutions may be different from the expectations of all the various critical stakeholders like learners, teachers and parents. These multifaceted differences among the critical stakeholders in educational institutions exert pressure on all the stakeholders and the pressure is more on the learners.

Educational institutions are noted as places of learning where such attempts to facilitate, enhance and promote learning professionally and pedagogically incorporate sound and logical organization of the instructional space, where the teacher promotes order and harmony, formulates and implements rules and regulations and correspondingly prioritizes the maintenance of discipline. Conscious and systematic efforts of educational institutions in these attempts to promote learning are characterized by different levels of communication such as between learners and learners, between teachers and learners, between learners and other personnel and between teachers and other personnel in the educational institutions. The possibility of communication at any of the levels mentioned above to violate rules and regulations that govern educational institutions particularly in the classroom is possible but the frequency of such communication between student and student and student and teacher violating rules and regulations in educational institutions is higher. So, behaviours that lead to the violation and breaking of rules and regulations in educational institutions mostly occur in the course of communication particularly in the classroom.

That the above is the case about educational institutions point in the direction that all the critical stakeholders particularly students can bring into the educational institution different behaviours, most of which can be bad and all such bad behaviours compete for space and can be unleashed in one instructional space called the classroom or the larger school premises. The fact that bad behaviours are epically and phenomenally common in educational institutions make educational institutions one social institution where rules and regulations are the norm, pillar and the livewire of their success and existence. The inevitability of rules and regulations makes discipline an ever-present phenomenon in educational institutions. As a rule and regulation governed social institution, stakeholders in educational institutions can resort to discipline and disciplinary actions and measures when stakeholders in the education industry, knowingly and unknowingly violate the rules and regulations that govern educational institutions.

We have earlier stated that discipline is a polymorphous concept and what this means in reality is that the meaning of the concept of discipline in one context may not be its meaning in another context. Discipline in the context of military institutions does not have the same meaning with discipline in the context of educational institutions. Discipline in the context of military can mean strict and excessive enforcement of power that prioritizes a command mentality kind of blind obedience and absolute compliance with the directives of a superior whereas discipline in the context of education and educational institutions has a

multiplicity of meanings. According to Konstrantinou et al (2015:235), discipline in the instructional space, that is, classroom in educational institutions is any measure taken by a teacher to ensure the sustenance of conditions that can contribute to the uninterrupted conduct of educational process and consequently to the achievement of the school's pedagogical objectives while Mbithi (1974) writes that discipline within the classroom or school and educational context is any act of control of a class to achieve desirable behaviour.

Anyone who critically, analytically and reflectively scrutinizes the above definitions and interpretations of discipline in educational institutions can quickly come to the realization that discipline in educational institutions simply revolves around stakeholders in education providing instructions, guidance and developing in learners and demonstrating through their own actions and conducts, skills and attitudinal dispositions for self-discipline, self-control and self-confidence on one hand and implementing collectively agreed decisions whose targets are to serve as basis for deriving authority for actions that can deter those whose actions and behaviours constitute moral infractions from continuing such actions.

No doubt, one cardinal objective of the school is to maintain order and safety for all the members of the school community through discipline but one million dollars question is: who is responsible for initiating actions that results in the discipline of the members of the school community? Some scholars simply hold the teacher and the school responsible for the discipline of the members of the school community, a development that points finger to more than one entity. If we take it that it is the school and the teacher that should discipline, discipline here can only be meted out on the learners by the teacher and who disciplines the teacher in the event that he misbehaves? We can say and say it strongly that the responsibility of disciplining members of the school community or members of educational institutions is and should be a collective responsibility, more persons should be involved namely learners, teachers, parents, other members of staff of school or educational institutions who are not teachers and finally the government.

From what has been said above, discipline in educational institutions is a conglomerate of actions that involves many stakeholders for its objectives and effectiveness to be translated into reality and again expecting or carrying out discipline and disciplinary actions in schools and educational institutions is an enigma. Scholars and researchers hold different views above discipline and disciplinary measures and each sound especially appealing and at the same time leaves a word of caution. Onderi, and Odera (2012), write that schools and educational institutions as rules and regulations governed organizations must not compromise or undermine issues of discipline or punishment in schools and educational institutions. The above scholars solidify the need for discipline or punishment in schools and educational institutions by specifically noting that "we need punishment in schools to create conditions for good learning atmosphere since there is enough evidence to show it helps learning" (p. 773), and "that teachers need to educate children through punishment to learn and even to become aware of the things they should not do to avoid being punished" (p.714). On the reverse side, the same scholars acknowledge that "punishment as a disciplinary measure has the power to not only demoralize a learner in the school or educational institution but can cause a child to hate to come to school" and once a child is no longer willing to learn, then the positive values of punishment in education becomes less important: What is more revealing about punishment or disciplinary measures in the school or educational institutions is also their observation that "any teacher who is not aware of the consequences surrounding punishment can be prosecuted" (p.712). This means that teachers can suffer some severe consequences in their attempts to discipline learners. The enigma about discipline and disciplinary measures in schools and educational institutions is more pronounced when one examines the actions and behaviours of parents especially when teachers take disciplinary actions against their children. Parents and the society are interested and desirous that the teacher or the school disciplines their sons, daughters and wards, but the same parents whose requests for disciplinary actions against their sons, daughter and wards may have been favourably considered quickly turn out to assault, abuse, insult, molest, arrest, arraign and prosecute the teacher in courts of law and the society that decries and laments the rate of indiscipline and other forms of bad behaviours emanating from learners in schools and educational institutions in the present times and expect teachers and educational institution to do something about it always turn around to castigate teachers,

calling them names and condemning them in strong and unprintable terms as people who are least fit and least suitable to teach and manage learners any time learners complain of disciplinary actions against them in the school or educational institutions. What this translates into is that the teacher and educational institutions are not safe in the hands of the students, parents and the members of the society in their attempts to diligently and honestly discharge their statutory duties, which in all ramifications are in the best interests of the learners and the society.

Having pointed out such enigmatic and chameleonic nature of discipline in educational institutions, it is also pertinent to identify and highlight possible causes or sources from where indiscipline and disciplinary challenges that are fast becoming norms in schools and educational institutions emanate from. There are multiple and multifaceted variables that introduce and cause disciplinary challenges in schools and educational institutions and this pointedly means that disciplinary challenges in schools and educational institutions cannot be blamed on one particular source alone. It is a fact that cannot be disputed that virtually all stakeholders in educational institutions and forces outside schools and educational institutions cause systemic distraction and disruptive behaviours that support and promote indiscipline and correspondingly cause disciplinary challenges in schools and educational institutions particularly during teaching and learning in the classroom. We can say and say it very strongly that the student or the learner is a major cause of disruption and distraction in the process of teaching and learning in the classroom. Students naturally come from different backgrounds and are easily influenced by the different backgrounds and minimal other influences from the outside world that have potentials to produce in them undesirable behaviours, which they manifest and demonstrate in the course of teaching and learning in schools and educational institutions.

The manifestation and demonstration of these disrupts, interferes and distracts both the teacher and the learners during teaching and learning and consequently raises disciplinary challenges for the teacher in the classroom. Part of how the influence from fellow learners and the outside world generate epic and phenomenal disciplinary challenges is that every learner in the class has a different belief system, different culture and equally different expectations from their participation and involvement in the activities that go on in the classroom and in the school. Every day experience shows that learners do not respond the same way in the face of simple, sophisticated and complex issues from fellow students or learners or the outside world, however, sufficient evidences show that learners easily embrace and identify with influences that align with the demonstration and manifestation of infertile, juvenile, flamboyant or destructive traits that on their own pose disciplinary challenges to the teacher in the course of teaching and learning.

Apart from the learner, the teacher is a critical stakeholder that we can say authoritatively can be a major source of behavioural and other attitudinal disorders that stimulate, produce and ignite distraction, interference and disruption in the course of teaching and learning in schools and educational institutions. A teacher who lacks the professional competencies expected of a teacher such as proper mastery of his subject matter, knowledge of the sociology and psychology of the learners, a teacher who lacks knowledge of how to initiate creative interactions with his learners or who cannot create a stimulating learning environment that can trigger or raise the curiosity of the learners to learn, a teacher who undermines the personality of his learners, a teacher who lacks integrity or who is morally compromised or a teacher whose habit or way of dressing distracts the attention and concentration of learners has on his own consciously laid foundations for disorderly, disruptive, distractive and uncontrollable behaviours from the learners and these in all honesty and sincerity have potentials to limit his productivity in the classroom and by extension his contributions to the human capital base of his state, but most disastrously the behaviours and actions of such a teacher is a recipe for igniting disciplinary challenges from his learners.

Apart from students and teachers who are critical stakeholders in teaching and learning and whose actions and activities cause disciplinary challenges in the form of stimulating disorder, disruption and distraction in teaching and learning in the classroom, school and educational institutions, the general environment, the location of a school and current events or happenings such as the socio-cultural, political and economic climate of a state at any particular point in time can be stimulators of disruption, distraction and

disorder in teaching and learning in the classroom, school and educational institutions. Schools that exist in structures that constitute security risks to learners and teachers, schools that exist very close to motor parks, events centres and other noisy environments where noise pollution especially music and advertising are common, the prevalence of poverty so much that learners hardly eat from their homes or receive fundamental or basic healthcare or maintenance and general insecurity occasioned by current global menace of terrorism, kidnapping, banditry, ritual murder and ritual killing that promote and generate feelings of psychological and emotional fear of the unknown especially among learners help to cause disciplinary challenges in schools and educational institutions. These not-too-good developments develop in learners the capacity to continuously reflect and disorderly respond to the regrettable situations by constituting themselves into discussion groups in the classroom and in the school possibly on how to chart out strategies for survival even when classes are going on. We can say and say it very strongly that the impressionable age of learners can compel them to be easily attracted to sounds of music, advertisement and jingles so much that despite being in class for learning purposes, learners can sing and dance to the rhythms of such distractions. Again, the prevailing atmosphere of fear can filter and instill into the mind of learners' feelings of frustration, hopelessness, helplessness, and general disenchantment so much that learners look up to the future with extraordinary sense of pessimism and a mindset that instills in them that paying attention to instructions in the classroom and learning after all has no meaning because the future is monumentally, epically and phenomenally bleak. As nature has no space for vacuum, the possibility of learners in these circumstances occupying themselves with behaviour that pose disciplinary challenges to the teacher and the school is very high.

What had been said above can be said to be pointing in directions that many variables are responsible for disciplinary challenges in schools and educational institutions. The learner or more pointedly classmates, the teachers, the nature of a school and more importantly environmental forces that are beyond the learners and the control of the teachers topically cause disciplinary challenges in schools and educational institutions. It therefore follows that causes of disciplinary challenges in educational institutions can be reduced to simply two factors namely;

- i. Factors within the school (micro factors)
- ii. Factors outside the school (macro factors)

Distractions, disorderly behaviours and disruptions in teaching and learning that trigger disciplinary challenges that owe their roots to inadequate provision of teaching and learning facilities and infrastructure, distractions and disruptive issues that border on inadequate number of personnel such as teachers' inability to show capacity as professionals in all ramifications of professional competence and disruption, disorderly behaviours and distractions that are as a result of personality traits or dispositions of learners are good examples of factors that cause disorderly, disruptive and distractive behaviours within the school (micro factors) while factors outside the school that can cause disorder, disruptive, distraction or disciplinary challenges in educational institutions have their backgrounds in socio-economic, socio-cultural and political forces that may be prevalent in an environment in which an educational institution is situated, fall within the frame of reference of macro factors.

CONCLUSION

Discipline is one concepts that individuals, institutions and states pray that it becomes a norm in the day-to-day affairs of man and the society. Because it is conceived as a desirable practice and process, there is hardly any institution instituted by man across every society of the world that does not lay emphasis on discipline. That the above is the case has made discipline elastic, so elastic that it attracts multifaceted interpretations that in all honesty demand anyone who is discussing the concept to call attention to the particular context in which the concept is being used. In this study, focus is on understanding discipline in educational institutions.

Discipline is a fundamental necessity in educational institutions and why this is so is that all the stakeholders – students, teachers and parents come from different background, share different values and have different expectations from educational institutions. Interestingly, educational institutions are to

satisfy the curiosity of all the stakeholders and sure foundational and fundamental guarantee for making all these possible is the extent in which educational institutions make discipline a norm.

Discipline in educational institutions is unique as it invokes meanings that revolve around measures that are supportive of meaningful institutional delivery or meaningful teaching and learning, any systematic measure used in effectively and efficiently controlling a class so as to achieve desirable behaviour from stakeholders in educational institutions, any measure employed by the management of educational institutions to ensure that teaching and learning environment is safe and orderly especially the maintenance of a culture of peace, order that is free from violence and social atmosphere in educational institutions that promote and support developing in learners behavioural dispositions and abilities for self-discipline, self-confidence and self-control. Discipline in the context of educational institutions rules out the use of external control mechanisms that are mainly punitive in attempts to make learners conform to socially acceptable standards of behaviour rather makes case for the prioritization of dialogue, co-operation, persuasion, mutual respect and the recognition of the fundamental human rights of whoever is to be disciplined and the target can focus on instilling in learners the ability to be rational especially the capacity to demonstrate self-confidence, self-discipline, self-control and ethically and morally acceptable behavioural dispositions for harmonious living in the society. Anyone who critically scrutinizes discipline from the angle educational institutions conceives it can situate discipline as being deep-rooted in moral rationality and corresponding a practice and a process that is not for purpose of inflicting pain.

The above understanding of discipline provides safeguards for stakeholders in educational institutions particularly the teachers, who are seen as the ones who must maintain or serve as custodians of discipline in educational institutions. Parent as stakeholders in educational institutions are desirous that their children should be disciplined in educational institutions but the same parents usually turn around to beat up teachers, arrest teachers and arraign teachers before courts of law when teachers discipline their children. It is possible to think along lines where the understanding of discipline by teachers in educational institutions maybe an imposition of the meaning of discipline from other institutions, a development that can force parents to take actions against the teachers in educational institutions.

This is the enigma of discipline in educational institutions and the irony of it all is that teachers who find themselves in the web of crisis and confusion that results due to their active participation in issues that border on the discipline of learners usually suffer the consequences as they remain without any one to protect and defend them. True, discipline is necessary in educational institutions but the realities of the 21st century demand that discipline in educational institutions be viewed from new lens. First, we need to acknowledge that most teachers in educational institutions do not have sufficient ideas and sufficient knowledge about discipline especially the implications of disciplining learners from the angles of punitive measures and the implications of disciplining learners from the perspective of developing learners' capacities for self-confidence, self-discipline and self-control. Sufficient awareness and sufficient insights on these can give rise to paradigm shift, new theorizing and new developments that can be beneficial to educational institutions in particular and humanity generally.

Educational institutions as rules and regulations governed social institutions can involve parent and the government in making rules and regulations, that concern discipline in educational institutions and in such rules and regulations, parents and the government can authoritatively suggest disciplinary measures that can be applied in educational institutions for the different offences that learners commit and if need be, parents and the government can administer the appropriate disciplinary actions against particular offenders.

Formulation of rules and regulations aside, teachers who are critical stakeholders in educational institutions and who are the implementers of discipline and disciplinary actions in educational institutions can strive to minimize the occurrence of indiscipline through conscious initiation of good and positive relationships among stakeholders in educational institutions. It is a fact that cannot be disputed that cordial and harmonious relationship among stakeholders in educational institutions especially between teachers and students (learners) is key for making the teachers and the learners work cooperatively, a development that can help reduce indiscipline to its barest minimum.

All the foregoing reveals that there are micro and macro variables that stimulate, promote and support disciplinary challenges in educational institutions. On this basis, government and investors in educational institutions should be more careful, sensitive and critical in the choice of areas where they locate educational institutions. In the same way, government and her agencies should stop granting operational permit to investors very close to educational institutions. There are establishments whose proximity to educational institutions are sure recipe for deviant and disciplinary challenges. The availability of the right serene environment for teaching and learning that is free from noise that comes from motor parks and the location of educational institutions far from commercial areas can limit the distractions and challenges of discipline that such areas cause to learners.

Most learners lack basic training from their home and are easily lured into gangs and gang activities and some learners hardly take breakfast before going to school. These group of students in educational institutions can easily identify with persons or environments that provide them with alternatives and correspondingly initiating social justice measures that can empower parents or any form of family support programmes can be a step in the right direction for placing students on the right track where they can avoid deviant behaviours.

Deriving from all these, every teacher should create and devote time to reflect adequately on discipline and its challenges in educational institutions bearing in mind that variables outside the control of the teacher and educational institutions are responsible for the multifaceted disciplinary challenges in educational institutions and after such reflections, individual teachers can work towards developing their own autonomous philosophy of action for handling and responding to the complex and hydra-headed challenges of discipline in educational institutions.

REFERENCES

- Ageeva, V (2016): Theories of social construction in anglophone historical epistemology in 2010-2015. *SHS Web of conference* 28. DOI, 10.105/shsconf/20162801113.
- Agulana, C (2011). Ethics and education. In A.F Uduigwomen & K. Ogbinaka (eds). *Philosophy of Education: an analytical approach*. Joja Educational research and publishers Limited.
- Aminigo, I.M (1999). *A direct introduction to philosophy of education*. Hanging Garden Publishers
- Angadi, G.R (2019). Philosophical method of educational research in Engineering, *International Journal of Research in Engineering, IT and social sciences* 9(1) 39-41 January
- Currie, A (2021). Science and speculation. <https://doi.org/10/007/510670-020-00570-2>
- Eboh, M.P (1996). *Philosophical essays: Critique of social praxis*. Paragraphics.
- Gire, A (2020). Speculation. In V. Glavaneau (ed).The Palgrave Encyclopedia of possible MacMillian. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-9835-5160-1>
- Haug, L, Xie, Y & Chen, X (2021). A review of function speculative thinking. *Frontiers of psychology*. 12.728 946.doi:10 3389/Fpsy.2021.728946
- Ishitiaq, S & Naz, S (2024). Present status early childhood care & education (ECCE) centers with reference to NEP 2020 in district Srinagar: An explanatory study. *Inquiry: An educational Journal* 41 May
- Konstantinou, I. C, Chatzisavva, E.A. & Logotheri, S. G. (2022). The role of school discipline from the students' point of view. *World Journal of Education Research* 9(5): 56-78
- Liu, C. H & Matthew, R (2005). Vygotsky's philosophy: Constructivism and its criticism examined. *International Education Journal* 6(3) 386-399
- Mbithi, D (1974). *Foundations of School Administration*. Oxford University Press.
- Nwaokugha D.O & Agbarakwe, H.A (2024). Early Childhood care and education: revolutionary and functional foundations for national development in Nigeria. *International Journal of Research and Review* 11(9): 250-263 September
- Nwaokugha D.O & Wogonwu, H.W (2020). Analytic philosophy: Exploring its potentials and advantages in education in Nigeria. *Educational Journal of multi-disciplinary Studies*. (EJMUDIS) 9(1); 108-188

- Nwaokugha D.O & Wogonwu, H.W (2023). Prospects of online teaching and learning in Nigeria. *International Journal of Education, Learning and Development* 11 (2), 1-15
- Nwaokugha, D. O. & Keri-Frank, F. (2023). Online teaching and learning during covid-19 in Nigeria: Prospects, challenges and revelations. *International Journal of Research and Review*, 10(3), 78-98.
- Nwaokugha, D. O. (2022). Entrepreneurship and entrepreneurship education in Nigeria: A search and initiative in a Postmodern tradition. *International Journal of Research and Review*, 9(4), 157-170.
- Nwaokugha, D.O & Moses, A. (2025). Promoting cooperation between teachers and learners in the classroom. *International Journal of Innovative Education Research*, 13 (4); 431-451, Oct- Dec.
- Nwaokugha, D.O & Nwaogu, O.A (2024). Prioritizing teacher quality in early childhood care and education in Nigeria. *International Journal of Innovative Psychology and social development*. 12(4) 60-74, Oct – Dec
- Nwaokugha, D.O & Odinka, E. O (2025). Career choice in early childhood care and education: A socio-philosophical analysis. *International Journal of Innovative Education Research*, 13 (3), 177-192, April – June.
- Nwaokugha, D.O & Rotimi – Aina, O.B (2025). Early Childhood care and Education in Malaysia and Nigeria: a comparative analysis. *International Journal of Innovative Psychology and Social Development*, 13(2) 108-122. April-June
- Nwaokugha, D.O & Smith- Ogizeh, Q.C (2025). Challenges of teaching in early childhood care and education in Nigeria. *International Journal of Innovative Psychology & Social Development* 13(1) 154-170 Jan – Mar
- Nwaokugha, D.O (2015). Private Sector participation in university education in Nigeria. In J.O Ajuonuma, J.D Asodike & R.O Anyaogu (eds). *Issues and trends in change and innovation in Nigeria Education system*. Pearl Publishers International Ltd.
- Nwaokugha, D.O (2021). Exploring sport as effective engagement mechanism for youth empowerment and youth development in Nigeria’s Niger Delta region. *Archives of Business Review*. 9(3), 157-180.
- Nwaokugha, D.O (2025) - Understanding the classroom and classroom management strategies. *International Journal of Innovative Educational Research* 13 (4): 21-39, Oct-Dec
- Nwaokugha, D.O & Danladi S.A (2016). Language and communication: effective tools for educational inspection and supervision in Nigeria. *Mediterranean Journal of Social Sciences* 7(3):420 – 428
- Oderi, N. L. E & Odera, F Y (2012). Discipline as a tool for effective school management. *Educational Research*, 3(9), 710-716
- Oduor, R.M.J (2010). Research methodology In philosophy within an interdisciplinary and commercialized African context: guiding against undue influence from social sciences. *Thought and practice: A Journal of Philosophy Association of Kenya (PAK)*. New Series: 2(1), 87-118
- Shively, W.P. (2005). *Power and choice: An introduction to political science*. Mc Graw Hill
- Silverman, H. J. (1991). Introduction: The philosophy of postmodernism. In H. J. Silverman (ed). *Postmodernism-philosophy and the arts*. Routledge.
- Swedberg, R (2021). Does speculation belong in social science research? *Sociology Method and Research* 50(1), 45 – 74
- Were, N. (2006). *Discipline, Guidance and counselling in schools*. Nekema Publishers.
- Zeeman L, Poggenpoel, M, Myburgh, C. & Van der linde, N. (2002). An Introduction to a postmodern approach to educational research: Discourse analysis. *Education* 123 (1): 96-102